

Data Stewardship of Governmental Administrative Data: Governance, Maturity and Diversity in the Brazilian context

Policy Brief

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Executive summary

Core problem: Brazilian governmental administrative data, particularly those produced by Health Information Systems (SIS), face critical challenges regarding governance, quality and representativeness. The statistical invisibility of diversity groups persists despite legislative advances, compromising the design, implementation and monitoring of equitable public policies.

Key findings:

- Data management maturity in national health systems is heterogeneous, with weaknesses in infrastructure, documentation and data literacy.
- The collection of diversity data (race/color, ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation) is limited, fragmented and conditioned by specific legal frameworks that determine the entry points for this information in the systems.
- Political decisions become, in effect, data policies, but without an institutional framework of data stewardship, lineage and provenance that ensures transparency and accountability.
- The absence of guiding principles for the treatment of diversity data perpetuates epistemic and operational distortions that negatively impact the public policy cycle.

Main recommendations:

1. **Strategic:** Establish National Principles for Data Stewardship of administrative data, inspired by the Aurora Principles, OCAP and inclusion by design guidelines.
2. **Institutional:** Create formal data stewardship instances with clear mandates for governance, lineage documentation and quality assurance.
3. **Operational:** Standardize the collection of diversity variables across all information systems, with mechanisms for self-identification, informed consent and protection of sensitive data.

1. Context and policy problem

1.1. Administrative data as critical state infrastructure

Electronic administrative records generated by governmental information systems constitute critical infrastructure for the exercise of essential state functions: the production of official statistics, the design and evaluation of public policies, the monitoring of rights and governmental transparency. These data, originally created for operational purposes, have become central inputs for population data science and evidence-based research.

In the field of Brazilian public health, systems such as the Mortality Information System (SIM), the Live Birth Information System (SINASC) and the Notifiable Diseases Information System (SINAN) capture information about vital and health events of national scope. The digitalization of these records, initiated in the 1990s, potentialized their use for statistical, epidemiological and surveillance purposes.

"Health information systems have functioned as instruments for the production of raw data destined for the construction of statistical indicators about the population. When combined, they capture comprehensive information about life trajectory, from birth, through disease occurrence, to death." (Souza, 2024)

1.2. The diversity question as a political and epistemic problem

Diversity data, categories such as race/color, ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation, belonging to traditional peoples and communities, possess life and social history. They are not neutral. They are generated in specific contexts, mediated by legal frameworks that reflect trajectories of rights recognition and struggles for citizenship.

The statistical invisibility of these groups compromises the State's capacity to formulate equitable policies, monitor discrimination and promote social justice. However, the simple inclusion of fields in forms does not guarantee quality, completeness or adequate use of this information. Issues of technological infrastructure, institutional capacity, ethical principles and regulatory frameworks determine whether and how this information is effectively collected, preserved and utilized.

"In some aspects, legislation may restrict the presence of this information and delimit the collection entry point and, with this, bias or promote analysis distortions. Decisions around social regulations become data and information policies." (Souza, Radar Cidacs, 2024)

1.3. Limits of current governance and institutional maturity

The digital trajectory of the Brazilian public sector has advanced significantly since the 1990s, but data governance remains fragmented. Between 2010 and 2018, 54 health information systems of national scope were identified, operated in a decentralized manner by states and municipalities. This fragmentation results in:

- Redundant collection of the same information by different systems, with distinct methods and rules;
- Data discontinuity in system version changes;
- Absence of standardized documentation on ontologies, metadata and business models;
- Limited capacity for interoperability and linkage between databases;
- Lack of formal data stewardship instances responsible for quality, lineage and data lifecycle.

These weaknesses become even more critical in the context of the Digital Health Strategy and initiatives for data opening, interoperability and use of artificial intelligence. The absence of guiding principles and robust governance exposes data to risks of inadequate use, perpetuation of biases and violation of rights.

2. Evidence and diagnosis

2.1. Data management maturity model: health systems diagnosis

The Health Data Management Maturity Report evaluated six national systems (SINASC, RESP-Microcephaly, SINAN, VIGITEL, e-SUS Notifica and SIM) according to six critical components:

- **Data management:** collection, storage, update, transparency and communication processes.
- **Data quality:** monitoring of precision, completeness, consistency and timeliness.
- **Data standards:** adoption of standardized regulations and classifications (e.g., ICD-10, IBGE categories).
- **Data infrastructure:** technological resources, architecture, scalability and integration capacity.
- **Data access:** availability of anonymized microdata, public platforms (e.g., TabNet).
- **Data literacy:** user training, technical documentation, support tools.

Main findings:

Component	SINASC	RESP	SINAN	VIGITEL	e-SUS	SIM
Data management	4	3	3	4	4	4
Data quality	4	3	3	4	4	4
Data standards	4	4	3	4	4	4
Infrastructure	3	2	3	4	3	3
Data access	4	4	4	4	4	4
Data literacy	3	3	3	3	3	3

Legend: 5 = Optimized | 4 = Managed | 3 = Defined | 2 = Initial | 1 = Nonexistent

Results interpretation:

- **Management and quality:** Consolidated systems (SINASC, VIGITEL, e-SUS, SIM) present elaborated practices, but SINAN faces consistency challenges, including underreporting of congenital anomalies and use of garbage codes.
- **Infrastructure:** Critical heterogeneity. RESP-Microcephaly (score 2) presents difficulties in exporting and processing; SINAN has different architectures between versions. SINASC and SIM still depend on offline versions.
- **Data literacy:** Uniformly limited (all with score 3). Technical documentation is not widely available online, and there is no systematic investment in user training.

2.2. Capacity for diversity data collection

Analysis of the presence of diversity variables in the systems reveals minimal and fragmented capacity:

System	Sex	Race/Color	Ethnicity
SINASC	✓	✓	Indirect
SINAN	✓	✓	Indirect
VIGITEL	✓	✓	X
e-SUS Notifica	✓	✓	✓
SIM	✓	✓	Indirect

Critical gaps:

- **Gender identity and sexual orientation:** collected exclusively in SINAN-Violence (since 2015). Absent in other systems, including the HIV/AIDS module of SINAN, which uses proxies such as men who have sex with men (MSM).

- **Traditional peoples and communities (TPCs):** specific field present only in e-SUS Notifica and SISVAN (Food and Nutrition Surveillance System). In other systems, identification is indirect via address field or through the combination of indigenous race/color and address.
- **Race/color information quality:** SIM and SINASC have higher completeness due to the legal framework for civil registries (Law 6.015/1973). Information collected by third parties (health professionals, death declarants), with potential bias and inconsistencies.

2.3. Tensions between legislation, institutional practice and infrastructure

The incorporation of diversity data in health systems is mediated by specific legal frameworks that determine the entry points for this information:

- **Race/color:** Ordinance n° 344/MS (2017) made collection mandatory in all HIS, but the trajectory goes back to Ordinance GM/MS n° 3.947 (1998). Law n° 12.288/2010 (Statute of Racial Equality) and Ordinance n° 992/GM/MS (2009) established the National Policy for Comprehensive Health of the Black Population (PNSIPN).
- **Ethnicity/TPCs:** Decree n° 6.040/2007 (National Policy for Sustainable Development of Traditional Peoples and Communities). Legal recognition linked to territory and land regularization. Collection associated with socio-territorial diagnosis and social assistance policies (Unified Registry).
- **LGBT:** Ordinance n° 2.836/MS (2011) instituted the National Policy for Comprehensive LGBT Health. Collection of sexual orientation and gender identity limited to SINAN-Violence (Ordinance MS/GM n° 104/2011), reflecting the association between this data and mandatory violence notification.

This legislative fragmentation results in:

- Collection conditioned to the event that originated the system (e.g., violence for LGBT, birth/death for race/color);
- Absence of standardization between systems about which variables to collect and how;
- Analysis distortions when data from one system are generalized to the entire population;
- Technological infrastructure does not keep pace with the complexity of categories (e.g., absence of options for non-binary gender).

"It is noted that the collection of social information on diversity encounters the influence of the colonial past and regionalism. And it must overcome the challenges: crisis of the welfare state, xenophobia and rigid categorizations of minority groups." (Maturity Report, 2024)

2.4. Ontological and epistemological discussion of administrative records

Administrative data are not neutral representations of reality, but sociotechnical constructions that:

4. **Reflect the State's administrative categories** (who is recognized as indigenous, quilombola, transsexual), not necessarily the subjects' self-determination of identity.
5. **Are mediated by collection instruments** (forms, records), which limit and condition possible responses.
6. **Carry historical trajectories** of inclusion/exclusion, visibility/invisibility, that need to be made explicit.
7. **Imply epistemological choices** about what counts as evidence, how diversity is measured, and who has the authority to define these categories.

The absence of documentation about these choices, about the ontology of systems, the epistemology of collection, the lineage of data, compromises scientific validity and institutional accountability. The use of artificial intelligence and database linkage amplifies these risks, as algorithms trained on biased data reproduce and intensify distortions.

3. Guiding principles for data stewardship

Given the diagnosed challenges, it is imperative to establish a principled framework for the stewardship, governance and use of governmental administrative data. Principles have a finalistic character: they point to an ideal state of affairs and guide decision-making in contexts of uncertainty or regulatory gaps.

3.1. Aurora principles: conceptual reference

The Aurora Principles, developed in the context of analyzing Brazilian health systems, propose an integrated structure for the responsible treatment of administrative data, with emphasis on:

- **Data stewardship:** formal institutional responsibility for managing the data lifecycle, from collection to archiving or disposal.
- **Lineage and provenance:** systematic documentation of the origin, transformations and usage history of data, ensuring transparency and traceability.
- **Quality and completeness:** continuous monitoring of precision, consistency and representativeness.
- **Inclusion by design:** systematic incorporation of diversity variables from system conception, with mechanisms for self-identification and protection of sensitive data.
- **Ethical interoperability:** system integration respecting principles of data minimization, specific purpose and consent.

3.2. Indigenous data sovereignty

The Indigenous Principles establish that:

- **Ownership:** Indigenous communities have collective rights over data that represent them.
- **Control:** governance over collection, use and interpretation of data must involve these communities.
- **Access:** communities must have priority access to data concerning them.
- **Possession:** physical/digital custody of data must respect informational sovereignty.

These principles, although developed for specific contexts, offer a participatory governance model applicable to other diversity groups.

3.3. Articulation with LGPD and collective rights

The General Data Protection Law (LGPD, Law nº 13.709/2018) establishes legal bases for the processing of personal data, including sensitive data (race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, etc.). For governmental administrative data, the applicable legal bases are:

- **Public interest:** proportional to the purpose, respecting fundamental rights.
- **Execution of public policies:** provided that it is foreseen in law or regulation.
- **Statistical purposes:** with anonymization or pseudonymization whenever possible.

However, the LGPD was designed to protect individual rights. For diversity data, which involve collective rights (traditional communities, ethnic groups), a complementary framework is necessary that:

8. Recognizes the collective dimension of data;
9. Establishes mechanisms for community consent and participation in governance;
10. Guarantees transparency about how data are used for policies affecting these groups;
11. Prevents discriminatory or stigmatizing uses.

3.4. Stewardship, lineage and provenance as institutional guarantees

The absence of formal data stewardship results in:

- Fragmentation of responsibilities among technical areas, without clear mandate;
- Loss of institutional knowledge in management changes;
- Impossibility of tracing the origin of errors or biases in data;
- Lack of accountability about decisions on collection, anonymization or sharing.

The institutionalization of data stewardship functions, with rigorous documentation of lineage and provenance, is a necessary condition for:

- Reproducibility of analyses;
- Auditability of use;
- Public trust in governmental data.
- Preservation of institutional memory across administrative transitions;
- Efficient response to technical inquiries without duplicating reconstruction efforts;
- Valid temporal comparisons and trend analysis in policy evaluation.

4. Public policy recommendations

The following recommendations are organized by intervention level (strategic, institutional, operational) and oriented toward immediate action, considering the context of fragmented governance and heterogeneous maturity of Brazilian systems.

4.1. Strategic level: national policy and legal frameworks

4.1.1. Establish National Principles for Data Stewardship

- **Action:** Publish joint Resolution from the Ministry of Health / National Data Protection Authority (ANPD) establishing National Principles for Data Stewardship of governmental administrative data.
- **Minimum content:** (a) Formal data stewardship with defined attributions; (b) Mandatory documentation of lineage and provenance; (c) Inclusion by design of diversity variables; (d) Participation of affected communities in data governance; (e) Transparency about data use and transformations.

4.1.2. Harmonize legislation on diversity data collection

- **Action:** Promote legislative review to standardize the collection of race/color, ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation and belonging to traditional peoples and communities across all health and social security information systems.
- **Justification:** Current legislative fragmentation conditions collection to specific events (birth, violence, territory), limiting cross-sectional analyses and equity monitoring.

4.2. Institutional level: managing bodies, committees and stewardship

4.2.1. Create formal data stewardship instances

- **Action:** Designate data stewards in each health information system managing body (Department of Epidemiological Analysis and Surveillance of Non-Communicable Diseases, DAENT, Health Surveillance Secretariat, SVS, etc.).
- **Attributions:** (a) Document data model, ontology and epistemology of each system; (b) Maintain data lineage registry (transformations, linkages, anonymizations); (c) Monitor quality and completeness; (d) Ensure LGPD compliance and ethical principles; (e) Respond to access requests and audits.
- **Profile:** Professional with technical training in data management, knowledge of public health and institutional competence to articulate technical and legal areas.

4.2.2. Establish National Committee for Diversity Data Governance

- **Action:** Create, by Decree, permanent advisory Committee with representation from: (a) system managing bodies; (b) researchers in population data science; (c) civil society organizations representing diversity groups; (d) ANPD; (e) IBGE.
- **Mandate:** (a) Propose collection and categorization standards; (b) Assess impact of form changes; (c) Review linkage requests or AI use; (d) Promote community participation in data decisions.

4.3. Operational level: systems, forms, documentation, training

4.3.1. Standardize diversity variable collection

- **Immediate action:** Review forms of all health systems (SINASC, SINAN, SIM, VIGITEL, e-SUS, SISVAN) to include mandatory fields:

- Race/color (self-declaration, IBGE categories, option other and prefer not to say);
- Ethnicity/belonging to TPC (with updated list of peoples/communities);
- Gender identity (categories: cisgender woman, cisgender man, transgender woman, transgender man, non-binary person, other, prefer not to say);
- Sexual orientation (heterosexual, gay, lesbian, bisexual, asexual, other, prefer not to say).
- **Collection principles:** (a) Self-identification whenever possible; (b) Informed consent for sensitive data; (c) Prefer not to say option in all fields; (d) Clear and accessible language; (e) Training of health professionals on respectful approach.

4.3.2. Document ontology and data lineage

- **Action:** Publish, for each system, technical documentation covering:
 - Data model (entities, attributes, relationships);
 - Variable dictionary with operational definitions;
 - Version history and form changes;
 - Anonymization and pseudonymization processes applied;
 - Legal bases for collection of each variable;
 - Known quality/coverage limitations.
- **Format:** Online documentation, versioned, accessible via transparency portal. Public repository on GitHub or equivalent.

4.3.3. Invest in technological infrastructure

- **Action:** Prioritize modernization of systems with low infrastructure scores (RESP-Microcephaly = 2; SINAN, SINASC, e-SUS, SIM = 3).
- **Necessary investments:** (a) Migration to scalable cloud architectures; (b) APIs for interoperability; (c) Elimination of parallel offline versions; (d) Implementation of automated data quality pipelines; (e) Backup and recovery systems.

4.3.4. Develop national data literacy program

- **Action:** Create permanent training program for: (a) health professionals who collect data; (b) managers who use data for decision-making; (c) analysts and researchers.
- **Content:** (a) Importance of quality data collection; (b) Respectful approach in collecting sensitive data; (c) Use of tools (TabWin, EpilInfo, R, Python); (d) Interpretation of diversity data considering social context; (e) Ethics in data use.
- **Modality:** Distance learning with regional in-person workshops. Mandatory certification for system managers.

5. Implementation implications

5.1. Necessary institutional capacities

Implementation of the proposed recommendations requires:

12. **Inter-ministerial coordination:** Ministry of Health, ANPD, Ministry of Management and Innovation, Ministry of Human Rights and Citizenship, IBGE.
13. **Budget investment:** Modernization of technological infrastructure (estimate: R\$ 50-80 million over 3 years); hiring or training of data stewards (estimate: 20-30 positions at federal and state levels); development of documentation platforms.
14. **Technical capacities:** Professionals in data science, software engineering, information security, digital law, public health and social sciences.
15. **Social participation:** Institutionalized mechanisms for consultation with representative organizations of diversity groups.
16. **Political will:** Recognition, by senior management, that data stewardship is an essential state function, not a secondary activity.

5.2. Risks of non-implementation

Maintaining the status quo implies:

- **Perpetuation of statistical invisibility:** Public policies will continue without adequate information about impact on vulnerable groups.
- **Amplification of algorithmic biases:** Increasing use of AI and machine learning on biased data will reproduce and intensify discrimination.
- **Erosion of public trust:** Affected communities will perceive that their data are collected without care, transparency or benefit.
- **Loss of scientific opportunities:** Research based on administrative data will have questionable validity.
- **Non-compliance with LGPD:** Absence of documentation on purpose, lineage and legal bases exposes public bodies to legal questioning.

5.3. Initial monitoring indicators

To assess progress in implementing the recommendations, it is suggested to monitor:

Dimension	Indicator	Target (3 years)
Governance	% of systems with designated data steward	100%
Documentation	% of systems with published lineage documentation	80%
Diversity collection	% of systems collecting race/color, ethnicity, gender identity	100%
Quality	Average completeness of diversity variables	> 85%
Infrastructure	Average infrastructure maturity score	≥ 4
Training	Number of professionals trained in data literacy	> 5,000

6. Conclusion

Governmental administrative data constitute public heritage and critical infrastructure for the democratic exercise of governance. In the health field particularly, these data ground epidemiological surveillance, service planning and equity monitoring. However, analysis of the management maturity of Brazil's main systems reveals institutional weaknesses that compromise the quality, representativeness and reliability of this information.

The statistical invisibility of diversity groups, indigenous peoples, quilombola communities, LGBT population, among others, is not a technical accident, but the result of political and epistemic choices that materialize in fragmented legal frameworks, limited technological infrastructures and absence of formal data stewardship instances. These gaps not only perpetuate inequalities, but amplify risks in the context of data opening, interoperability and use of artificial intelligence.

The institutionalization of data stewardship principles, inspired by the Aurora Principles, OCAP and inclusion by design guidelines, is a necessary condition for transforming data governance in Brazil. This implies recognizing that data stewardship is a strategic state function, requiring: (a) formal and transparent responsibility; (b) rigorous documentation of lineage and provenance; (c) participation of affected communities in decisions about collection and use; (d) investment in infrastructure and training; (e) articulation between data protection legislation, collective rights and sectoral policies.

The recommendations presented in this policy brief are technically viable, politically urgent and ethically imperative. Their implementation will require inter-ministerial coordination, budget investment and, above all, political will to recognize that data quality determines public policy quality.

The decision to act or not in face of this evidence will define whether Brazil will advance toward a data governance that promotes equity and justice, or whether it will continue reproducing, in its official statistics, the exclusions that mark its history.

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